

Station: Manufacturing CO₂

 \triangleq 6 kg CO₂eq

Select your scenario!

from **A** (CO₂ -low)
to **D** (CO₂ -high)

Guiding questions:

The guiding questions help you gradually understand the differences between the scenarios and maintain an overview.

No
blocks

A

B

C

D

I have my own smartphone or similar device [A].

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Fairphone /
SHIFTphone.

Nothing /
iPhone /
Samsung.

Google Pixel /
Huawei /
Xiaomi.

My smartphone is ...

... received
from relatives.

... second-hand
purchased.

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... newly
purchased.

My device is ... years old.

... > 3 years

... 3 years

... 1-2 years

... < 1 year

I use the device ...

... a few times
per week.

... < 1 hour per
day.

... 1-3 hours per
day.

... > 3 hours per
day.

The smartphone's power saving mode is ...

... the device is
now turned off.

... always on.

... from time to
time on.

... never on.

When the device is no longer needed, I will ...

... pass it on.

... dispose it
properly /
recycle it.

... put it away.

... throw it
away.